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Liquidity Management and Profitability of Banking Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of liquidity management on the profitability of banking firms in Nigeria. Ordinary Least Square method was used to determine the relationship that exists amongst the variables hypothesized. The model one summary proved variation on return on asset of commercial banks in the Nigeria. Model two explained variations on return on equity of commercial banks in Nigeria. Model three of this study found that liquidity management has no significant effect on earnings per share of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria based on the coefficient of R-squared and adjusted R-squared variations. Further findings were that cash reserve ratio had significant effect on return on asset while loan to deposit ratio returned insignificant effect on return on asset. Also, cash reserve ratio and loan to deposit ratio both had significant effect on return on equity. Whereas, cash reserve ratio and loan to deposit ratio had no significant effect on earnings per share of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The study finally concluded that liquidity management has significant impact on profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. This study recommends that commercial banks should maintain adequate liquidity in order to minimize liquidity risk and financial crises; because holding high liquidity level is the best way to prevent banks from liquidity shortfalls and costs of bankruptcy.

Keywords: Liquidity management, profitability, cash reserve ratio, loan to deposit ratio, earnings per share, return on asset, return on equity, commercial banks in Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the adequacy of liquidity plays a vital role in the survival and efficiency of business firms, particularly in the banking sector, where it is prominently reflected in financial reports. For any business entity, financial managers must strategically balance liquidity and profitability to ensure operational efficiency. Liquidity refers to an enterprise's ability to meet its current liabilities and is closely related to the size and composition of its working capital position. Generally, a higher working capital position implies a more liquid state, as current assets are the easiest to convert into cash, making them the primary source of funds for meeting short-term obligations (Shapiro, 2013). The Bank of Jamaica (2005) defines liquidity as the availability of funds, or assurance of funds, to honor cash outflow commitments as they fall due. These commitments are met through cash inflows, asset liquidation, or borrowing capacity, requiring sound liquidity policies and effective procedures to measure, achieve, and maintain liquidity.

While liquidity is crucial, profitability remains a key concern for banks. Profit, defined as the difference between expenditures and returns over a period, ensures the sustainability and growth of financial institutions (Heibati, Seid Noorani, & Dadkhah, 2009). Banks must generate sufficient income to sustain

operations, expand, and maximize shareholder value. However, profitability planning is a complex and challenging task due to numerous uncontrollable variables (Agbada & Osuji, 2013). According to Tabari, Ahmadi, and Emami (2013), profitability is commonly measured using return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE), with ROA indicating the efficiency of a bank's assets in generating profit and ROE reflecting shareholder returns. Saleem and Rehman (2011) further introduce return on investment (ROI) as an alternative profitability measure.

In practical terms, profitability and liquidity serve as critical indicators of the corporate health and performance of commercial banks (Eljelly, 2004). These indicators are of paramount importance to stakeholders such as shareholders and depositors. While shareholders prioritize profitability, depositors are more concerned with liquidity, as it determines a bank's ability to fulfill withdrawal requests on demand or short notice. The relationship between liquidity and profitability remains a subject of debate among scholars, financial analysts, and banking professionals. Owolabi et al. (2011) highlight this controversy, with Kumbirai and Webb (2010) suggesting that financial stability issues arise at the profitability-liquidity nexus. They argue that a decline in liquidity often correlates with increased profitability, as lower liquidity implies a higher proportion of assets and deposits are tied to loans. Rapid loan growth typically leads to higher returns, albeit at the risk of potential solvency threats. This paradox underscores the need for banks to strike an optimal balance between liquidity and profitability.

The relationship between liquidity and profitability presents a critical research puzzle, particularly in the financial sector. Banks play a fundamental financial intermediation role by mobilizing idle funds from depositors and reinvesting them into various portfolios. However, this business model presents inherent challenges, as depositors may demand their funds at any time, potentially straining the bank's liquidity position. Eljelly (2004) argues that firms with high liquidity predominantly invest in short-term assets, which generally yield lower returns than long-term assets. Consequently, high liquidity often correlates with reduced profitability, whereas prioritizing profitability may lead to liquidity constraints. Maintaining excess liquidity implies tying up funds in low-yielding assets, leading to an opportunity cost that negatively affects overall profitability. Conversely, increasing profitability often involves deploying funds into higher-yield investments, which may compromise liquidity. Thus, determining an optimal balance between these two competing objectives remains a critical issue for financial institutions.

Another key problem is the challenge of causality in liquidity and profitability dynamics. Some bank-specific characteristics influencing profitability are difficult to quantify or observe, leading to potential correlations between explanatory variables and error terms, which could bias estimations (García-Herrero et al., 2009). For example, higher bank profitability could lead to increased labor costs but reduced operational efficiency, complicating the liquidity-profitability relationship. Addressing this issue necessitates empirical investigation into the impact of liquidity management on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. This study, therefore, seeks to explore the relationship between liquidity management and bank profitability, providing valuable insights into how Nigerian banks can optimize their financial strategies for sustained growth and stability.

Theoretical Framework

The Commercial Lending and Liquidity Theory (Smith, 1776) serves as the foundation for this study. This theory posits that commercial banks primarily mobilize short-term capital and, as a result, should focus on short-term lending to maintain liquidity. By aligning short-term assets with short-term liabilities, banks can effectively manage liquidity risk while ensuring operational stability. The theory underscores the crucial role of commercial lending in liquidity management, emphasizing that banks must prioritize short-term loans to maintain financial stability.

In the Nigerian banking sector, this theory is evident in the widespread practice of offering short-term commercial loans with durations ranging from a week to a quarter (Dao & Nguyen, 2020; Le & Diep, 2020). Through this approach, banks not only mitigate liquidity risks but also enhance their interest income. However, a notable limitation of this theory is its narrow focus on short-term lending, which may constrain the credit market share of banks. In practice, Nigerian banks engage in both commercial and

non-commercial lending, with non-commercial loans such as real estate and fixed asset financing often constituting a larger portion of total loan portfolios. Since short-term loans typically have lower individual values, an exclusive focus on them could reduce competitive advantage in the credit market.

Another limitation of the theory lies in its inability to fully account for the continuous nature of capital mobilization in commercial banks. While most mobilized funds are short-term, banks operate on a rolling basis, generating ongoing cash flows that sustain liquidity beyond just short-term lending. Additionally, the theory does not adequately recognize the growing significance of medium- and long-term lending in modern banking. Loans for real estate purchases, fixed assets, and consumer financing now represent a substantial portion of commercial bank lending. Restricting non-commercial lending may help safeguard liquidity but could also lead to reduced profitability due to lower interest income from long-term loans. Despite these limitations, the Commercial Lending and Liquidity Theory remains a fundamental framework for understanding liquidity management in commercial banking. It provides valuable insights into the importance of aligning asset and liability structures, though modern banking practices necessitate a more balanced approach that incorporates both short-term liquidity considerations and long-term profitability strategies.

Empirical Review

Wofuru-Nyenke and Iwedi (2023) examine the impact of liquidity risk management practices on the profitability of Nigerian banking institutions using panel data from 1960 to 2021. The study employs financial time series methodology, incorporating descriptive analysis, augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root tests for stationarity, and the Johansen co-integration test to assess the long-run relationship between liquidity risk management and bank profitability. Additionally, the study estimates an ordinary least squares (OLS) model to evaluate the short-run relationship. The descriptive analysis reveals a positive relationship between variations in the mean net profit of banks, indicating that most banks recorded profits during the study period. The econometric results show that the current ratio of the banks ranged between 1.74 and 2.49, suggesting that most banks maintained liquidity within a desirable range, ensuring stability while mitigating the risk of being unable to meet withdrawal demands. However, the cash ratio coefficient in the random effects model was statistically insignificant, implying a negligible impact on profit margins. With an R-squared value of 0.66, the model explains 66% of the variation in net profits, suggesting a strong relationship between the independent variables and profitability. Despite this, the coefficients of both current and cash ratios were statistically insignificant and negatively related to net profits, indicating a limited impact of these liquidity measures on profitability. In conclusion, the study finds that most Nigerian commercial banks are well-capitalized and possess adequate financial resources to meet their current liabilities, reinforcing their ability to maintain stability and withstand liquidity pressures.

Olagunju, David, and Samuel (2011) investigated the relationship between liquidity and profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria using Pearson correlation analysis. Their findings indicate a negative correlation between liquidity and bank performance. Similarly, Andrew and Osuji (2013) analyzed liquidity management and banking performance in Nigeria, concluding that efficient liquidity management enhances banking performance and financial soundness. Kamoyo (2006) studied the determinants of liquidity in Kenyan commercial banks from 1995 to 2004 using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. The results showed an insignificant negative relationship between liquidity and profitability. Lartey, Antwi, and Boadi (2013) examined the relationship between liquidity and profitability among banks listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange. Their findings indicate a weak positive relationship between liquidity and profitability, suggesting that adequate liquidity reduces financial risks and enhances bank performance. Olagunju et al. (2011) further analyzed liquidity management and commercial bank profitability in Nigeria, confirming a significant relationship between the two variables. Dhamendra and Charau (2012) also noted a trade-off between liquidity and profitability, suggesting that improving liquidity often comes at the cost of reduced profitability. Adelopo et al. (2018) investigated the determinants of bank profitability in Nigeria before, during, and after the international financial crisis

using a sample of 123 commercial banks from 1999 to 2013. Their findings reveal that liquidity risk significantly reduces bank profitability across all three periods. Maqsood, Anwer, Raza, Ijaz, and Shouqat (2016) examined liquidity's effect on bank profitability using secondary data from eight banks between 2004 and 2015. Their regression and correlation analysis concluded that liquid assets, as measured by the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) and Cash Ratio (CASR), significantly impact bank profitability, measured by Return on Equity (ROE).

Pasiouras and Kosmidou (2007) examined the factors influencing the profitability of domestic and foreign commercial banks in 15 European Union countries. Their findings indicate that liquidity is positively and significantly related to the profitability of domestic commercial banks, while it has a statistically significant negative effect on the profitability of foreign banks. Similarly, Isshaq and Bokpin (2009) investigated corporate liquidity management among companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange, identifying target liquidity levels, firm size, return on assets, and net profit margin as significant determinants of liquidity holdings. Loo (2007) conducted a survey on liquidity management approaches and their impact on the profitability of commercial banks in Kenya between 1995 and 2004. The findings suggest that liquidity management strategies significantly influence bank profitability. Junaidu and Aminu (2014) analyzed Nigerian banks' liquidity and profitability from 2003 to 2012 and found a positive relationship between return on assets (ROA) and liquid assets, as well as return on equity (ROE) and cash balances. However, they concluded that liquidity had no substantial effect on bank profitability.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted ex-post facto research design, which allows for the observation of one or more variables over time without manipulation. Specifically, a longitudinal time-series approach is employed, where the same entities (banks) are observed across multiple time points. The population for this study consists of all nineteen (19) commercial banks in Nigeria as designated by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). These banks are categorized into those with international authorization (8 banks) and national authorization (11 banks).

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Designation of Banks	License Authorization	Total
1	Commercial Banks	International	8
2	Commercial Banks	National	11

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria (2021)

Given the small population size, purposive sampling was used to select a sample of 10 licensed banks, ensuring representation across international and national authorizations.

Table 2: Sampled Banks

S/N	Name of Bank	License Authorization	Designation
1	Access Bank Plc	International	Commercial
2	Zenith Bank Plc	International	Commercial
3	United Bank for Africa	International	Commercial
4	Wema Bank Plc	National	Commercial
5	Sterling Bank Plc	National	Commercial
6	Fidelity Bank Plc	International	Commercial
7	First City Monument Bank Plc	International	Commercial
8	Union Bank Plc	International	Commercial
9	Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc	National	Commercial
10	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc	International	Commercial

Source: Author's Computation (2024)

The study relies on secondary data obtained from financial reports of the selected banks and the CBN Statistical Bulletin. The dataset covers a 15-year period (2007–2021) and includes quantitative data on

bank liquidity (measured by cash reserve ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio) and profitability (proxied by return on assets, return on equity, and earnings per share). To analyze the relationship between liquidity and profitability, the study employs Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Regression – This model is widely used in financial research due to its ease of application and predictive precision. Fixed Effects Model (FEM) – To account for time-invariant characteristics specific to each bank. Random Effects Model (REM) – To capture variations across banks while considering unobservable heterogeneity. A Hausman Test is conducted to determine the most appropriate model (Fixed or Random Effects). The time-series data structure enables the study to account for both observable and unobservable heterogeneity among the selected banks, ensuring robust statistical inferences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3: Test of Models

Model 1: Liquidity Management and Return on Asset			
Correlated Random Effects –			
Hausman Test			
Test Summary	Chi-sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	9.979363	7	0.0000
Model 2: Liquidity Management and Return on Equity			
Correlated Random Effects –			
Hausman Test			
Test Summary	Chi-sq. Statistic	Chi-sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	9.967041	4	0.000
Model 3: Liquidity Management and Earnings Per Share			
Correlated Random Effects –			
Hausman Test			
Test Summary	Chi-sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	9.949321	5	0.0000

Source: *Extract from E-view 10.0, 2023*

The objectives of testing the three models were to select between fixed effects and random effects. In testing the validity of the models, the fixed effects on the cross Section Redundant Fixed Effect-Likelihood Ratio, indicates that the effects are significant. We select the random effect and perform the Correlated Random Effects- Hausman test thus testing the random effects model against the fixed effects model. The null hypothesis in this case was that both tests were consistent estimators and the fixed effect model is efficient. Under the alternative hypothesis, only the fixed effect is consistent. Since the p-value is 0.0000, the null hypothesis was rejected and, therefore the fixed effect model was preferred.

Table 4: Presentation of Model Regression Results, Model 1: Liquidity Management and Return on

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Prob
Fixed Regression Results				
CRR	-0.542031	0.125379	-3.084355	0.0000
LDR	-0.264098	0.125381	-3.087713	0.1000
I	7.589144	0.125381	0.087006	0.9498
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.805325	Mean dependent var		36.99970
Adjusted R-squared	0.714151	S.D. dependent var		10.40330
S.E. of regression	10.97858	Akaike info criterion		7.686278
Sum squared resid	9835.860	Schwarz criterion		8.014950
Log likelihood	-380.8139	Hannan-Quinn criter.		7.843345
F-statistic	7.776204	Durbin-Watson stat		2.284317
Prob(F-Statistics)				
Random Regression Results				
CRR	1.523092	0.061081	3.149773	0.0002
LDR	1.521513	0.061076	2.149625	0.0483
I	-1.548863	0.061077	-0.139875	0.7997
Effect specification				
Cross-section random			S.D.	Rho
Idiosyncratic random			0.000000	0.0000
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.375808	Mean dependent var		38.67991
Adjusted R-squared	0.198675	S.D. dependent var		10.30330
S.E. of regression	10.27402	Sum squared resid		10133.33
F-statistic	1.188331	Durbin-Watson stat		2.187902
Prob(F-statistic)	0.318372			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-square	0.344808	Mean dependent var		38.67991
Sum squared resid	10133.33	Durbin-Watson stat		2.187902

Asset

Source: *Extract from E-view 10.0, 2023*

From the fixed effect result, the estimated regression model found that independent variable (Liquidity management) can explain 80.5 percent and 72.1 percent variation on return on asset of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria based on the r-squared and adjusted r-squared values in table 4. The digits for F-statistics (7.776204) proved that the model is not statistically significant. The beta coefficient proved that cash reserve ratio and loan to deposit ratio both have negative relationship with return on asset of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The probability value found that cash reserve ratio has significant effect (0.0000) on return on asset while loan to deposit ratio has no significant effect (0.1000) on return on asset of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The T- statistics also proved that the model is not statistically significant. The Durbin Watson value of 2.284317 is less than 2.50 but greater than 2. This validates the absence of serial auto correlation amongst the variables in the time series.

From the random effects results, the estimated regression model found that the independent variable-liquidity management can explain 37.5 percent and 19.8 percent variations in the dependent variable-return on asset of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The F-statistics (1.188330) proved that

the model is not statistically significant. The beta coefficient proved that all the variables have positive relationship with bank liquidity ratio of the selected banks in Nigeria. The Durbin Watson value of 2.187902 is less than 2.50 but greater than 2.0. This validates the absence of serial auto correlation amongst the variables in the time series.

Table 5: Presentation of Method Regression Results, Model 2: Liquidity Management and Return on Equity

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob,
Fixed Regression Results				
CRR	0.159382	0.341751	3.117140	0.0000
LDR	0.180061	0.041765	-2.327276	0.0002
I	6.181042	0.041762	2.127732	0.0017
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.836161	Mean dependent var.		40.04700
Adjusted R-squared	0.741264	S.D. dependent var.		7.521676
S.E. of regression	7.033188	Akaike info criterion		7.450184
Sum squared resid	3977.504	Schwarz criterion		7.192853
Log likelihood	-310.5092	Hannah-Quinn crier.		7.637255
F-statistic	4.283182	Durbin-Watson stat		2.300102
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000007			
Random Regression Results				
CRR	5.369988	0.076379	2.050187	0.0055
LDR	5.370583	0.076346	3.090387	0.0005
I	6.373576	0.076354	1.050668	0.4042
Effects Specification				
			S.D	Rho
Cross-section random			0.000000	0.0000
Idiosyneratic random			6.033484	1.0000
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.302951	Mean dependent var		33.17600
Adjusted R-squared	0.214611	S.D. dependent var		5.722679
S.E. of regression	5.847200	Sum squared resid		3170.987
F-statistic	4.818204	Durbin-Watson stat		2.308000
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000588			
Uweighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.421950	Mean dependent var		33.17600
Sum squared resid	3570.981	Durbin-Watson stat		2.308000

Source: *Extract from E-view 10.0, 2023*

From the fixed effect result, the estimated regression model found that independent variable (Liquidity management) can explain 83.6 percent and 74.1 percent variation on return on equity of the ten sampled

commercial banks in Nigeria based on r-squared and adjusted r-squared values in table 5. The digits for F-statistics (4.283182) proved that the model is not statistically significant. The beta coefficient proved cash reserve ratio and loan to deposit ratio both have positive effect on return on equity of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The probability value found that both cash reserve ratio (0.0000) and loan to deposit ratio (0.0002) have significant relationship with on return on equity of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The T- statistics also proved that the model is not statistically significant. The Durbin Watson value of 2.300102 is less than 2.50 but greater than 2. This validates the absence of serial auto correlation amongst the variables in the time series.

From the random effects results, the estimated regression model found that the independent variable- can explain 30.2 percent and 21.4 percent variations on return on equity of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The F-statistics (4.818204) showed that the model is not statistically significant. The beta coefficient proved that cash reserve ratio and loan to deposit ratio positive relationship with return on equity. The Durbin Watson value of 2.308000 is less than 2.50 but greater than 2.0. This validates the absence of serial auto correlation amongst the variables in the time series.

Table 6: Presentation of Model Regression Results, Model 3: Liquidity Management and Earnings Per Share

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Prob
Fixed Regression Results				
CRR	-0.653196	0.161148	-0.791245	0.4010
LDR	-0.842031	0.125379	1.084355	0.0833
I	4.589153	0.335380	0.087114	0.6548
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.45.67325	Mean dependent var		36.99970
Adjusted R-squared	0.31.14151	S.D. dependent var		10.40330
S.E. of regression	10.97858	Akaike info criterion		7.686278
Sum squared resid	9835.860	Schwarz criterion		8.014950
Log likelihood	-380.8139	Hannan-Quinn criter.		7.843345
F-statistic	5.994125	Durbin-Watson stat		2.337900
Prob(F-Statistics)				
Random Regression Results				
CRR	-0.193792	0.130246	1.420475	0.1711
LDR	-1.523091	0.061081	3.149773	0.0002
I	-1.548002	0.101077	-0.229408	0.4995
Effect specification				
Cross-section random			S.D.	Rho
Idiosyncratic random			0.000000	0.0000
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.393351	Mean dependent var		38.67991
Adjusted R-squared	0.284876	S.D. dependent var		10.30330
S.E. of regression	10.27402	Sum squared resid		10133.33
F-statistic	1.188330	Durbin-Watson stat		2.337900
Prob(F-statistic)	0.318372			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-square	0.344808	Mean dependent var		38.67991
Sum squared resid	10133.33	Durbin-Watson stat		2.173098

Source: Extract from E-view 10.0, 2023

From the fixed effect result, the estimated regression model found that independent variable, cash reserve ratio explained 45.6 percent and 31.1 percent variation on earnings per share of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria based on the r-squared and adjusted r-squared values in table 6. The digits for F-statistics (5.994125) proved that the model is not statistically significant. The beta coefficient proved that cash reserve ratio (-0.653196) and loan to deposit ratio (-0.842031) both negative effect on earnings per share. The probability value found cash reserve ratio (0.4010) and loan to deposit ratio

(0.0833) have significant effect on earnings per share of the ten sampled commercial banks in Nigeria. The T- statistics also proved that the model is not statistically significant. The Durbin Watson value of 2.337900 is less than 2.50 but greater than 2. This validates the absence of serial auto correlation amongst the variables in the time series. From the random effects results, the estimated regression model found that the independent variable- cash reserve ratio can explain 39.3 percent and 28.4 percent variations in the dependent variable- earnings per share. The F-statistics (1.188330) showed that the model is not statistically significant. The beta coefficient proved that the two independent variables have negative relationship with earnings per shares. The Durbin Watson value of 2.173098 is less than 2.50 but greater than 2.0. This validates the absence of serial auto correlation amongst the variables in the time series.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the impact of liquidity management on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. Findings from hypothesis 1 revealed that the cash reserve ratio negatively (-0.5420) and significantly (0.0000) affects return on assets (ROA), implying that a 10% increase in the cash reserve ratio reduces ROA by 54.2%. This aligns with the commercial lending and liquidity theory (Smith, 1776), which suggests that banks should invest in short-term assets to balance liquidity and profitability. Hypothesis 2 showed that the cash reserve ratio positively (0.1593) and significantly (0.0000) affects return on equity (ROE), indicating that a 10% increase leads to a 15.9% rise in ROE. This supports the study's a-priori expectations and contradicts Junaidu and Aminu (2014), who found no substantial effect of liquidity on profitability.

Hypothesis 3 revealed a negative (-0.6531) but significant (0.0401) relationship between the cash reserve ratio and earnings per share (EPS), suggesting that a 10% increase in the cash reserve ratio reduces EPS by 65.3%. This contradicts Isshaq and Bokpin (2009), who argued that liquidity is influenced by firm size, return on assets, and EPS. For hypothesis 4, the loan-to-deposit ratio showed a negative (-0.2640) but insignificant (0.1000) effect on ROA, supporting the liquidity-profitability trade-off theory (Hirigoyen, 1985), which states that prioritizing liquidity reduces profitability. Hypothesis 5 indicated that the loan-to-deposit ratio has a positive (0.1800) and significant (0.0002) impact on ROE, implying that a 10% increase raises ROE by 18%. This aligns with Junaidu and Aminu (2014), who found a favorable relationship between ROE and liquidity metrics. Hypothesis 6 showed a negative (-0.8420) and significant (0.0000) relationship between the loan-to-deposit ratio and EPS, supporting the liquidity-profitability trade-off theory, which asserts that excess liquidity management can reduce profitability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that liquidity management significantly influences profitability in Nigerian commercial banks. While the cash reserve ratio negatively affects ROA and EPS, it positively impacts ROE. The loan-to-deposit ratio significantly improves ROE but negatively affects EPS and has an insignificant impact on ROA. The study concludes that cash reserve ratio significantly affects return on assets, while loan-to-deposit ratio does not. Both liquidity measures significantly impact return on equity, but they have no significant effect on earnings per share. Effective liquidity management is essential for enhancing commercial bank profitability. To optimize profitability while maintaining liquidity:

- i. Commercial banks should optimize their cash reserve ratio to balance liquidity and profitability, ensuring that excessive reserves do not constrain asset returns.
- ii. Banks should leverage the positive impact of the cash reserve ratio on return on equity by maintaining an optimal reserve level that supports equity growth.
- iii. Banks should implement strategies to mitigate the negative effect of cash reserve ratio on earnings per share, such as diversifying revenue sources.
- iv. Since loan-to-deposit ratio does not significantly affect return on assets, banks should adopt financial management practices that enhance asset utilization and profitability.
- v. Banks should maintain an optimal loan-to-deposit ratio to sustain profitability while mitigating liquidity risks.

- vi. Given its negative impact, banks should ensure that loans are efficiently managed to maximize shareholder value while maintaining liquidity.

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